

Raman spectra of α -Ta₂O₅: a first-principles analysis

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Abstract

We present a first-principles study of the vibrational spectra, i.e. vibrational density of states (VDOS) and Raman spectra, of amorphous tantalum. Model structures of up to three-hundreds atoms size have been generated by means of classical and *ab-initio* molecular dynamics and subsequently used for a series of *ab-initio* calculations of the vibrational spectra, including tests with different kinds of exchange-correlation functionals and pseudopotentials. Our study confirms that the vibrational modes above ~ 550 cm⁻¹ consist mainly of Ta-O stretching motion of O atoms, meanwhile Ta motion gives a major contribution to the VDOS only below ~ 200 cm⁻¹. In particular, the vibrational modes underlying the main Raman peak at ~ 670 cm⁻¹ are related to Ta-O bond stretching motions and a major contribution to the peak appears to come from twofold O atoms. Decomposition of the twofold O contribution to the VDOS in terms of rocking, bending, and stretching weights shows that above ~ 550 cm⁻¹ rocking and bending fade away, while the stretching component becomes largely dominant. Finally, by means of local projectional analysis we infer that vibrational modes with frequencies above 550 cm⁻¹, feature mostly asymmetric and symmetric (A_1) stretching modes of TaO_{*n*} ($n = 5, 6, 7$) polyhedra. The latter decomposition, in particular, may explain the origin of the experimental Raman doublet at ~ 830 and ~ 940 cm⁻¹ observed with 785 nm laser in Favaro *et al.* *Class. Quantum Gravity* **41**, 105009 (2024).

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Introduction

Amorphous tantalum (α -Ta₂O₅) is a fascinating material belonging to the class of intermediate oxides [1, 2] and unlike other oxide glasses such as SiO₂, it is not obtained through a *quench from the melt* procedure. Instead, high quality amorphous tantalum films are usually produced through ion-beam sputtering (IBS). Nowadays α -Ta₂O₅ is a material of paramount technological relevance for electronics and microelectronics applications (e.g. RRAMs [3, 4, 5]), especially because of its large static dielectric constant, (~ 25), and because of the considerably large electronic band gap (~ 5 eV). For instance, α -Ta₂O₅ thin films are used as gate insulators in microelectronics, having a lower leakage current and a greater capacity (for the same thickness) as compared to amorphous silica (α -SiO₂) films, leading to the production of more performing components. Because of its high refractive index, low extinction coefficient (in the visible) and small thermo-optic coefficient, amorphous tantalum thin films have several applications in optics and photonics, ranging from the production of lenses and of anti-reflection coatings for optical applications in the visible spectrum, near-UV and near-IR, to the production of microresonators [7, 6, 8]. In particular, combined with other amorphous oxides,

e.g. TiO_2 , $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ thin films are used for the coatings of the test-masses in the mirrors that make up the advanced LIGO/VIRGO gravitational wave detectors [9]. Yet, past and future technological development of the mirrors is driven by the imperative of reducing the so called *thermal noise*. The latter is due to fluctuations of the mirror surface under the random motion of particles in coatings and substrates [10, 11]. In the last decades the imperative of reducing thermal noise has motivated a huge amount of experimental research on thin films that has employed several techniques and considered many different materials candidates. For instance NMR and X-ray spectroscopies were employed to characterize the short- and medium-range order of $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ [12, 13]. Infrared and Raman spectroscopy has then been used in many studies e.g. to study annealing effects, the onset of crystallization, doping effects, and also to study pressure induced amorphization [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19].

Despite the tremendous technological importance of amorphous tantalum, well exemplified by the above mentioned applications, the current understanding of its microscopic structure is however roughly limited to the first and second neighbors shells. Analogously, the theoretical interpretation of the vibrational spectra of $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ is currently limited to the discussion of VDOS bands and related properties [20, 21, 22], meanwhile the analysis and theoretical modeling of the Raman (and infrared) spectra has remained a quite elusive topic. The Raman spectrum of $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ exhibits a prominent peak at $\sim 670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ together with minor features in the range $800\text{ to }1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [19, 23, 24, 17]. In Ref. [21], on the basis of classical molecular dynamics calculations [20], the main Raman peak was attributed to the bending and stretching motions of three-fold oxygen atoms. Yet, we note that classical force fields are not capable to describe the vibrational properties of amorphous oxides e.g. silica with a good accuracy [25], so it is reasonable to assume that a similar problem occurs when trying to describe the vibrational modes of amorphous tantalum.

In this work we take advantage of three viable model structures of amorphous tantalum generated by means of a combined usage of classical molecular dynamics and *ab-initio* approaches, including a fully *ab-initio* generated model. The comparison with the available experimental X-ray total correlation function allows us to discuss the reliability of our structural models of $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$, in particular validating our fully *ab-initio* generated model. For the set of adopted models we calculate vibrational spectra (VDOS, Raman) at *ab-initio* level which allow us to establish accurate assignments for the vibrational modes underlying the main peaks of the Raman spectra. In particular, by means of projectional analysis we show that stretching motion of twofold O atoms is dominating the VDOS above 550 cm^{-1} , and we infer that the asymmetric and symmetric (A_1) stretching modes of TaO_n ($n = 5, 6, 7$) polyhedra can lead to a doublet in the VDOS at frequencies above 800 cm^{-1} . Our analysis substantially improves upon the assignments done in Ref. [21], and suggests an assignment in terms of stretching modes of TaO_n polyhedra for the high-frequency VDOS doublet which could underlie the recent experimental Raman data (785 nm) of Favaro *et al* [17].

Methods

Ab-initio computational details

All the vibrational spectra calculated for $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ in this work are based on density functional theory (DFT). Structural relaxations and vibrational modes are obtained, in the harmonic approximation, by employing the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) i.e. the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) [26] functional and pseudopotentials from the standard solid-state pseudopotentials library optimized for precision or efficiency (SSSP) [28, 27]. The Kohn-Sham wave functions are expanded in a basis of

plane waves up to a kinetic energy cutoff of 50 Ry at the sole Γ -point of the Brillouin zone. For the electron density, a cutoff of 400 Ryd was used, consistently with the SSSP prescriptions [27].

The structural models of α -Ta₂O₅ (described herebelow) are relaxed by adopting force thresholds of 0.0025 eV/Å (or smaller), which allow for a proper harmonic treatment of the vibrational modes. We calculate the vibrational frequencies and eigenmodes, as well as the Raman derivatives tensors by means of the linear response based code `ph.x` of the QuantumEspresso package [29, 30]. Consistently with the current implementation [29] Raman derivatives have been obtained by employing LDA-PZ normconserving pseudopotentials [31] with an adopted threshold for self-consistency at most of 10^{-12} , whereas a smaller value, 10^{-14} , has always been adopted for the calculation of vibrational frequencies. In addition, the vibrational modes are obtained under the constraint that the total force constants satisfy the *acoustic sum rule*.

Models generation details

In this work we consider three viable model structures of amorphous tantalum. Two “hybrid” models, Model I and Model II with sizes of 336 and 126 atoms, were obtained [32] using classical molecular dynamics simulations through a *quench from the melt* procedure. The simulations were performed by using the LAMMPS code [33] and the classical potential developed by Trinastic *et al.* [20]). The adopted quench rate is ~ 10 K/ps, from a high T melt with T=5000 K and a total simulation time of 800 ps. The initial configurations were obtained from a β -Ta₂O₅ crystal cell by using a $3 \times 3 \times 2$ supercell (126 atoms), and a $4 \times 4 \times 3$ supercell (336 atoms). A third model, referred to as the full *ab-initio* model (Model III, containing 126 atoms) was obtained using *ab-initio* MD *quench from the melt* procedure: the liquid of Ta₂O₅ was thermalized at 3000 K with a 10 ps MD run (`pw.x` code), and then cooled down below the melting point in 20 ps. A thermostat with a stochastic-velocity rescaling was used [34]. The atomic positions of the models are then finally relaxed by first-principles using, for testing purposes, several different DFT flavours/setups: LDA-PZ [31], PBE-ONCV [35], PBE-SSSP [28]). The latter has then been chosen for the analysis and discussion of the Raman bands as explained in the section dedicated to the vibrational density of states. A force threshold of $\leq 2.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ eV/Å has been employed for the relaxation of atomic positions.

A direct visualization (e.g. with XCrySDen [36]) of the structure of Model II shows a layering of the atoms, and indicates that this model is reminiscent of a crystalline structure, as also it is apparent from the structural analysis presented herebelow. The crystallization tendency of Model II is likely to be related to the comparatively small size of the model [37]. Yet, since amorphous models that exhibit crystalline features might be of interest in the context of describing the onset of crystallization [17] we estimate Model II worth to be included in the present analysis.

Results

Structural analysis

Total correlation function and bond lengths

In Fig. 1(a) we compare the X-ray total correlation function, $T_X(r)$, as calculated using the RINGS code [38] for our models and as found in the experiment [13]. The first peak of $T_X(r)$ corresponds to the first peak of $g_{\text{OTa}}(r)$ [Fig. 1(b)] and is located at ~ 1.9 Å. The second and third peaks of $T_X(r)$ correspond to the first peaks in $g_{\text{OO}}(r)$ and $g_{\text{TaTa}}(r)$ and are found at ~ 2.71 Å, 3.26 Å and 3.73 Å,

Figure 1: (a) Theoretical X-ray total correlation function $T_X(r)$ as calculated (PBE-SSSP) for Model I (dot-dashed/blue), Model II (dotted/grey), and Model III (solid/red). For comparison the experimental $T_X(r)$ of Alderman *et al.* [13] is also shown (green discs). (b) Pair-correlation functions [38] $g_{\text{TaO}}(r)$ (solid/green), $g_{\text{TaTa}}(r)$ (dashed/red), and $g_{\text{OO}}(r)$ (dot-dashed/blue) of $a\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ as calculated for our *ab-initio* Model III. (a Gaussian broadening of 0.075\AA was applied to smooth the PCFs).

Table 1: Frequency (%) of coordination numbers of Ta and O atoms in the a -Ta₂O₅ models used in this study, obtained after *ab-initio* relaxation in PBE-SSSP. Experimental coordination frequencies, obtained from the ¹⁷O MAS NMR spectra of Ref. [12] are also given. The cutoff radius of $R_{\text{cut}} \simeq 2.6$ Å is used.

Coordination	Ta				O		
	4	5	6	7	2	3	4
Model I	-	27.1	57.3	15.6	65.0	34.6	0.4
Model II	-	22.2	66.7	11.1	64.4	35.6	-
Model III	-	38.9	50.0	11.1	71.1	28.9	-
Ref. [21]	0.5	28.5	69.4	1.6	69.6	30.1	-
Expt. [12]					57	43	-

respectively [13]. Peaks located at close positions were also reported in the experimental $g(r)$ obtained by analyzing the SAED patterns of the amorphous region [39]. Model I and III reasonably agree with the experimental data over all the reported lengths range. By contrast, the $T_X(r)$ of Model II shows a strong peak at about 5.2 Å which is absent both in the experimental data and in the correlation functions of the other models. We attribute this peak to the occurrence in Model II of atomic layers reminding of an orthorhombic tantalum phase. We also note that the shoulder related to the edge-sharing structures in Model I and II is located at a slightly larger distance (~ 3.36 Å) with respect to the corresponding peak in Model III (3.26 Å), which by contrast is well separated from the main peak at 3.72 Å.

In Fig. 1(b), we give the partial pair-correlation functions, $g_{\text{OTa}}(r)$, $g_{\text{TaTa}}(r)$, and $g_{\text{OO}}(r)$, corresponding to Model III, those of the other models being qualitatively similar. The first peak of $g_{\text{TaO}}(r)$ is located at 1.93 Å and agrees closely with the Ta-O bond length [13]. From a spherical integration of $g_{\text{TaO}}(r)$ up to its first minimum at ~ 2.6 Å, we derive an average coordination number of ~ 5.8 , consistently with the Ta coordination numbers in this model (Tab 1) that indicates a prevailing octahedral structural unit. The first peaks of $g_{\text{TaTa}}(r)$ correspond to Ta-Ta distances of 3.26 Å and 3.72 Å, respectively. These peaks reflect the Ta-Ta correlations occurring due to the presence of edge-sharing and corner-sharing polyhedra, respectively. The first peak of $g_{\text{OO}}(r)$ corresponds to O-O distances of 2.72 Å.

In Fig. 2 we show the distributions of Ta-O bonds as calculated for twofold and threefold oxygen atoms in our Models. The Ta-O bond (twofold O) distribution in Model I and III has a peak at 1.91 Å while Model II shows a peak at a smaller length of 1.89 Å. The FWHM for Model I is about twice the one of Model II and it is sensibly larger than in Model III. For all our models, the distribution of Ta-O bonds for three-fold oxygen atoms, Fig. 2(b), is considerably larger than found for the twofold oxygen atoms, Fig. 2(a), and shows a peak at longer distance (~ 2.1 Å) reflecting the weaker Ta-O bond with respect to the one of twofold O atoms.

Coordination numbers and edge-sharing polyhedra

Table 1 shows that oxygen atoms in our Models I and II have similar Ta coordinations i.e. the amount of twofold and threefold coordinated oxygen atoms is quite similar in the two models. However Model II features a larger number of six-fold coordinated Ta atoms with respect to Model I, reflecting the

Figure 2: (a) Distribution of Ta-O bonds as calculated for the twofold oxygen atoms in our α -Ta₂O₅ models. (b) Distribution of Ta-O bonds as calculated for the threefold oxygen atoms in our models (PBE-SSSP calculation). Gaussian broadening of 0.02 Å is applied.

crystalline-like tendency of the structure of Model II. By contrast, Model III shows the lowest amount of six-fold coordinated Ta atoms and largest amount of five-fold Ta atoms among the three models, together with a slightly larger number of twofold coordinated O atoms. By comparing with NMR data all our models considerably ($\sim 10\%$) overestimate the concentration of twofold oxygen atoms and underestimate the concentration of threefold oxygen atoms. Yet we note that NMR estimates might suffer of errors upto 5% [40].

The structure of amorphous Ta_2O_5 is known to contain a considerable fraction of edge-sharing polyhedra (ESP) as revealed by the X-ray pair distribution functions (PDF) which show a hump at ~ 3.4 Å due to the Ta-Ta correlations ($\sim 20\%$) from ESP structures ([13, 41] and Refs. therein). According to Prasai *et al.* [42] the amount of ESP might impact for the material mechanical loss. In fact, ESP polyhedra could be associated with two-level systems (TLS) that contribute to room temperatures mechanical loss [42]. In our models almost all the O atoms that belong to edge-sharing polyhedra (i.e. are found in four-atoms rings) are three-fold coordinated. Yet, e.g. in Model III, there are $\sim 10\%$ of O atoms belonging to edge-sharing polyhedra that are twofold coordinated. In any case, the number of O atoms in four-membered rings roughly corresponds to the number of O atoms that are three-fold coordinated.

Using a cutoff of 2.6 Å to define atomic coordination, we found that 72.2% of Ta atoms in Model III form edge-sharing TaO_n polyhedra. The remaining 27.8% Ta atoms form corner-sharing polyhedra. In Model I the Ta atoms forming edge-sharing polyhedra are about 77% while the remaining 23% form corner-sharing polyhedra. By direct inspection (XCrysden) most of the corner-sharing Ta polyhedra are actually Ta pentahedra. In fact more precisely in Model I we found that 64% of the Ta corner-sharing polyhedra are Ta pentahedra and the remaining 36% are Ta octahedra (six-fold coord.). Similarly in Model III we found that 60% of the Ta corner-sharing polyhedra are Ta pentahedra, with the remaining 40% due to six-fold coordinated Ta atoms. In Model II almost all (89%) of Ta atoms form edge-sharing polyhedra and the remaining 11% are all Ta corner-sharing pentahedra (i.e. 100% of the corner-sharing Ta polyhedra are penta-coordinated Ta atoms). The abundance of edge-sharing Ta polyhedra in Model II reflects an amorphous structure exhibiting crystalline-like ordering. None of the Ta in our models are in a face-sharing polyhedron. In Model I and III 85% and 80% of the six-fold coordinated Ta atoms form edge-sharing polyhedra. These findings suggest that the fraction of penta-coordinated Ta atoms is indicative of the amount of corner-sharing polyhedra in Ta_2O_5 so that a model structure containing a large number of penta-coordinated Ta atoms is likely to feature a high number of corner-sharing polyhedra.

Planarity of OTa_3 units

The threefold coordinated O atoms are found to approximately lie on the plane of their three Ta nearest neighbors, forming what is here called an OTa_3 unit. To evaluate the planarity of these units, that the next section will allow us to distinguish between *in-plane* and *out-of-plane* O motion, we define the ratio π_d as obtained by dividing the sum over the three Ta-O-Ta angles by 360° , which at most equals 1 for an ideal planar unit. In Model I π_d , on average, is 0.983, comparable to the value found for the most planar OAl_3 units in amorphous alumina [40], and almost all (91.5%) of the OTa_3 units can be regarded as planar i.e. they show a $\pi_d \geq 0.95$ corresponding to a sum of Ta-O-Ta angles larger than 342° . In Model II, all (100%) OTa_3 units are planar with an average π_d of 0.997 that is consistent with the layering tendency of its atomic structure and also with the fact that in the orthorhombic phase $\pi_d = 1.0$. In Model III the vast majority (77 %) of the OTa_3 units are planar,

Figure 3: (a) Vibrational density of states of Models I (dot-dashed), II (dotted) and III (solid) as calculated with PBE-SSSP setup. (b) Comparison of the VDOS calculated for Model III using LDA-PZ (dotted/green), PBE-ONCV (dot-dashed/blue) and PBE-SSSP (solid/purple) setups. In (b) the position of the main Raman bands is indicated with red ticks on the abscissa axis. A Gaussian broadening of 25 cm^{-1} is used.

consistently with a slightly lower average planarity degree (0.970) than found for Models I and II, thus suggesting a stronger amorphicity for the structure of Model III with respect to the atomic structures of Models I and II.

VDOS

In Fig. 3(a) and (b) we show the VDOS as calculated for our models of $\alpha\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ and as obtained for Model III by changing the DFT setup. For Model III the choice of the PBE-SSSP setup results in a good agreement with the position of the main Raman band (see also following section on Raman spectra). We also note that vibrational frequencies of the main bands in the VDOSs calculated by using LDA-PZ and PBE-ONCV setups are very close (difference $\sim 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) both for Model III and Model I (not shown). Three main broad bands could be distinguished in all the models [Fig. 3(a)], a first one extending from 0 up to $\sim 550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a central one between $\sim 550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a high frequency band $\sim 750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ – 1100 cm^{-1} . The bands show model-dependent shifts (e.g. peaks of central band are located at ~ 640 and 660 cm^{-1} in Model I and III respectively) that may reflect the different O local environment in the models (see Fig. 2 and Table 1). Although qualitatively

similar, as compared to Model I and Model III, the VDOS of Model II shows several sub-bands that reflects differences in the atomic structure. The VDOSs of Model I and III are quite similar except for frequencies around ~ 250 and ~ 800 cm^{-1} where the VDOS of Model I is sensibly larger than that of Model III. This could be understood as a consequence of the larger number of three-fold O atoms in Model I wrt Model III (Table 1).

VDOS decompositions

In Fig. 4(a) we provide a decomposition of the VDOS in terms of Ta and O weights for Model I (similar decompositions have been done also for the other models). Fig. 4(a) shows that Ta motion is relevant for vibrational modes below ~ 200 cm^{-1} while O motion gives the dominant contribution above ~ 250 cm^{-1} . In Fig. 4(b) and (c) we further decompose O motion, both for twofold O and threefold O atoms, in terms of stretching, rocking, bending projections [43]. For threefold O atoms of OTa_3 units, with the term rocking we hereafter refer to the *out-of-plane* motion of oxygen atoms, whereas stretching and bending directions refer to a basis for *in-plane* oxygen motion. The decomposition shown in Fig. 4(b) indicates that rocking motion of twofold oxygen atoms is dominant up to ~ 300 cm^{-1} , with a peak at 245 cm^{-1} . Bending motion of the twofold O atoms is dominant in the range ~ 300 cm^{-1} to ~ 520 cm^{-1} . Above ~ 520 cm^{-1} stretching motions become dominant, with peaks at ~ 650 cm^{-1} and at 930 cm^{-1} , while rocking motion completely disappears and bending motion is very weak and fades away at ~ 700 cm^{-1} . The decomposition shown in Fig. 4(c) indicates that rocking motion of threefold oxygen atoms has a maximum weight at ~ 300 cm^{-1} , while the stretching motion becomes dominant already above ~ 400 cm^{-1} , with a maximal contribution at ~ 500 cm^{-1} and with minor features at 650 cm^{-1} and 830 cm^{-1} . The ratio between the total contributions of threefold O atoms and twofold O atoms [inset of Fig. 4(c)] is maximal around 550 and 800 cm^{-1} , while at ~ 650 cm^{-1} it is about 1:2, thus reflecting the relative $\text{O}^{[3]}/\text{O}^{[2]}$ concentration ratio (Table 1).

In Fig. 5 we analyse the VDOS in terms of local projection on A_1 , i.e. the symmetric stretching, and “ T -like”, i.e. asymmetric stretching modes of TaO_n polyhedra [Fig. 5(b)]. The total projection on A_1 mode sums up to a peak at ~ 940 cm^{-1} , while it is negligible below ~ 700 cm^{-1} . The projection on T mode leads to peaks at about ~ 640 and ~ 860 cm^{-1} . Above ~ 700 cm^{-1} , the frequency separation (~ 80 cm^{-1}) between the projection peaks on A_1 and T -like modes [Fig. 5(a)] fairly well corresponds to the experimental split (~ 90 cm^{-1}) between the two peaks of the high frequency Raman doublet recently observed by Favaro *et al.* [17] with 785 nm laser. Incidentally we note that in glassy SiO_2 and P_2O_5 , of which the networks are based on corner-sharing tetrahedra, analogous high frequency doublets are observed (See [44, 45, 46] and Refs. therein). Moreover the strong contribution of the antisymmetric stretching mode of the TaO_n polyhedra around ~ 640 cm^{-1} is reminiscent of the analogous peaks in silica and P_2O_5 glasses at ~ 800 cm^{-1} [45, 46].

The analysis of Damart *et al.* [21] indicated that (twofold) oxygen rocking and bending motions are dominant around ~ 250 – 350 cm^{-1} , while oxygen stretching motions are dominant above ~ 650 cm^{-1} . Yet, due to the usage of classical interaction potential the decomposition [21] is not so reliable as far as concerns the details in the intermediate range ~ 250 – 600 cm^{-1} . In fact, in contrast to Damart *et al.* [21], the central band around 660 cm^{-1} , in Fig. 4(b), does not feature any relevant O rocking contribution, meanwhile in the O decomposition shown by [21] the rocking contribution of twofold O atoms significantly extends up to ~ 710 cm^{-1} , with a remarkably strong peak at ~ 600 cm^{-1} . Another evident difference of the *ab-initio* VDOS (Fig. 4) with respect to the VDOS calculated when using the Trinastic potential [21, 41] is that the latter completely closes the gap (~ 750 cm^{-1}) between the

Figure 4: (a) Decomposition of the VDOS of Model I (dotted/blue) in terms of Ta (dot-dashed/green) and O (solid) weights. (b) Decomposition of O motion in terms of bending (dot-dashed/green), rocking (dot-dashed/purple), and stretching (dotted/blue) projections for twofold coordinated oxygen atoms. (c) Decomposition of O motion in terms of rocking and stretching for three-fold O atoms. Inset: relative weight of threefold O atoms over twofold O atoms contribution to the VDOS. A Gaussian broadening of 25 cm^{-1} is used in all calculations

Figure 5: Contribution to the VDOS calculated for A_1 (solid/green) and T -like (dot-dashed/violet) modes of TaO_n polyhedra in Model I. For comparison of peaks location, the total VDOS (solid) and the sum of A_1 and T contributions (dotted) are also shown (b) sketch of A_1 and T modes used for projections illustrated e.g. with TaO_6 polyhedra. A Gaussian broadening of 20 cm^{-1} is used.

central band and the high-frequency stretching band which by contrast is well visible in the total VDOS of Fig. 4(a).

Raman

The experimental Raman spectrum of α -Ta₂O₅ exhibits a prominent peak at ~ 670 cm⁻¹ together with minor features in the range 800 to 1000 cm⁻¹ [19, 23, 24, 17]. A quite sharp feature ~ 445 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder at ~ 620 cm⁻¹ were considered as spurious by Galeener *et al.* [23], in particular they were attributed to strong forward Raman scattering in the TiO₂ prism material. Other minor features around ~ 470 cm⁻¹ and ~ 620 cm⁻¹ have also been reported eventually related to the presence of the silicon/silica substrate [47, 19]. The Raman data collected with laser 785 nm by Favaro *et al.* (R1 region of Fig. 2b of [17]) show besides the main peak at ~ 670 cm⁻¹ a well resolved high frequency doublet (~ 830 and ~ 935 cm⁻¹). Raman spectra of previous investigations (e.g. Galeener *et al.* [23] and Fontana *et al.* [19]) also suggest the presence of two subbands with possibly peaks at slightly larger frequencies ~ 850 cm⁻¹ and ~ 940 cm⁻¹.

In Fig. 6 we show the reduced Raman spectra (HH and HV polarizations [44]) as calculated for our amorphous tantala models. For all the models the HV spectrum only constitute a minor fraction of the HH intensity with a main peak in the range 640-680 cm⁻¹, so that the unpolarized spectrum is dominated by the HH component. The calculated HH Raman spectrum of Model I shows a prominent broad band in the range 600-700 cm⁻¹, in particular with two peaks forming a doublet at 630 cm⁻¹ and 700 cm⁻¹. The HH Raman spectrum of Model II features several quite sharp peaks at 225, 385, 485, 645, 737, 843 and 973 cm⁻¹ which suggest its structure may be reminiscent of a crystalline-like phase such as the low-temperature β form [19, 48] (The unpolarized Raman spectrum of a crystalline β -Ta₂O₅ powder sample given in Ref. [19] shows strong peaks at ~ 630 cm⁻¹, 705 cm⁻¹ (sharp), ~ 850 cm⁻¹, and a broad feature at ~ 500 cm⁻¹). The HH Raman spectrum of Model III features a main peak at about ~ 680 cm⁻¹ and a doublet at ~ 870 and 970 cm⁻¹ plus some minor features at 400 and 550 cm⁻¹, altogether providing the best frequency position and shape agreement, among the three models, with the main peak of the experimental Raman spectrum [17, 23, 19]. The peak at 970 cm⁻¹, can be ascribed to the A₁ symmetry stretching motion of TaO_n polyhedra (see Fig. 5) which reminds analogous peaks in silica and P₂O₅ glasses [49, 46]). The peak at ~ 870 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the asymmetric stretching motion of TaO_n polyhedra (compare with ν -P₂O₅ [46]) as suggested by Fig. 5). The observed frequency shifts (in particular for the highest frequency peak) between the models are likely to be related to the different Ta-O bond lengths (and different O local environment) and TaO_n distributions in the models.

In Fig. 7 we decompose the Raman spectrum of Model III into partial contributions of specific groups of atoms (Ta atoms, twofold O and threefold O atoms) by following the approach developed in Ref. [46]. An advantage of the approach [46] consists in the fact that the decomposition is additive. Fig. 7 indicates that the most interesting features of the HH Raman spectrum in the range 600 - 1000 cm⁻¹ arise mainly from the motion of the twofold O atoms. In particular, the contribution of threefold O atoms to the main Raman peak appears to be quite limited ($\sim 20\%$ of the contribution of twofold O atoms), meanwhile the Ta weight is practically negligible above ~ 250 cm⁻¹. This result quite closely echoes the VDOS decomposition [Fig. 4(c)]: at 670 cm⁻¹, the contribution to the VDOS of twofold O atoms is about twice the one from threefold O atoms. Moreover, the larger Raman coupling with O stretching motions exhibited by twofold O atoms with respect to threefold O atoms further enhances the contribution to the main Raman peak due to twofold O atoms.

Figure 6: (a) HH (solid lines) and HV (dotted lines) Reduced Raman spectra as calculated (PBE-SSSP) for Model I (blue), Model II (black), Model III (purple). All calculated spectra have been rescaled to match the integrated intensity of Model I. A Gaussian broadening of 20 cm⁻¹ is used. (b) For comparison the reduced spectra of Refs. [17] collected with 785 nm laser for R1 (discs/green) and R2 (discs/cyan) are also shown.

Figure 7: Decomposition [46] of the reduced (HH) Raman intensity, as calculated for Model III, in terms of twofold O atoms (red/dotted), threefold O atoms (red/dot-dashed), and Ta atoms (blue/dashed) contributions. Inset: ratio of the threefold O atoms and twofold O atoms contributions. A Gaussian broadening of 20 cm^{-1} was applied.

Conclusions

In this work we show that a fully generated *ab-initio* model (Model III) supports a picture of the $\alpha\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ network featuring a large number ($\sim 70\%$) of twofold O atoms ($\sim 10\%$ more than found with NMR). The *classical* interaction potential developed by Trinastic *et al.* [20] gives reasonable amorphous structures (e.g. Model I), but it should not be used to calculate vibrational modes, especially in the range ~ 500 to 1000 cm^{-1} , since it overemphasizes the weight of the oxygen rocking motion, that in our *ab-initio* VDOS is negligible above $\sim 500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and also since the VDOS calculated using the Trinastic potential [21, 41] closes the gap at $\sim 750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ between the central band and the high-frequency stretching band, which by contrast is well visible in our *ab-initio* VDOS. Raman spectrum calculated for Model II fairly agrees with Raman data of the R2 region in Favaro *et al.* [17] and with crystalline spectrum of Ref. [19], and thus might be regarded as a representative (transition) structure of amorphous tantalum at the onset of crystallization. Despite the considerably high amount of Ta atoms forming edge-sharing polyhedra we did not find any feature in the vibrational spectra of our $\alpha\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ models that could be related to ESP, apart from those related to the three-fold oxygen atoms that however reflects quite well the content of ESP: i.e. at the light of the present investigation only the vibrational features related to three-fold oxygen seem to be indicative of the presence of ESP.

The VDOS analysis of our $\alpha\text{-Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ models indicates that stretching motions of twofold-coordinated oxygen atoms dominate at frequencies above 550 cm^{-1} . At the light of the present investigation assignments of Raman bands based on Table 2 of Ref. [19] and references therein, as well as on Ref. [21] are rather incorrect since too much importance is given to triple-coordinated oxygen for the range $\sim 400\text{-}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [19], and in particular for the main Raman band at $\sim 670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. By contrast, the present investigation shows that stretching motion of twofold coordinated oxygen atoms is crucial as far as concerns the intensity of the main Raman peak at 670 cm^{-1} . Moreover, the contribution to the VDOS of threefold O atoms is maximized around ~ 500 and $\sim 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, with the relative ratio to the

twofold O weight being close to a minimum in the range $\sim 640\text{-}670\text{ cm}^{-1}$, in contrast to the previous attribution of the IR absorption peak at 640 cm^{-1} to the presence of OTa_3 units [14, 50]. Finally by projecting on local A_1 and T -like modes of TaO_n polyhedra, we show that the high-frequency doublet seen in the calculated VDOS, analogously to the similar doublets observed in $\alpha\text{-SiO}_2$ and $\alpha\text{-P}_2\text{O}_5$, mostly features symmetric stretching and asymmetric stretching modes of TaO_n ($n = 5, 6, 7$) polyhedra, which may help to explain the Raman data at 785 nm of Ref. [17].

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